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FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS: AN ALTERNATIVE APPROACH TO ENHANCE GASTRIC RESIDENCE TIME

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ABSTRACT

Gastric emptying is a complex process and one of the most important obstacles in the better absorption and enhances bioavailability of oral drug delivery system. In recent years various scientific and technological advancements have been made in the research and development of oral drug delivery systems to overcoming physiological adversities, such as short gastric residence times (GRT) and unpredictable gastric emptying time (GET). In order to avoid such adversities, efforts have been made to increase the retention time of the drug-delivery systems for more than 12 hour via floating drug delivery system Diverse attempts were being currently used including swelling and expanding system, polymeric bio adhesive systems, modified-shape systems, high density system and other delayed gastric emptying devices. The purpose of this review was to systemize recent approaches on floating drug delivery systems along with the principle mechanism of floation to acquired gastric retention.

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INTRODUCTION

Floating drug delivery systems (FDDS) are those systems which have a bulk density lower than gastric fluids and because of this, these systems remain buoyant (3-4 hours) for an extended period of time in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate.

The oral route is the most auspicious route of drug delivery. Controlled-release drug delivery systems (CRDDS) provide drug release at a predetermined, predictable and controlled rate which provides the benefits like maintenance of the optimum therapeutic drug concentration in blood with predictable and reproducible release rates for an extended time period, enhancement of duration of activity for short half-life drugs, elimination of side effects, reducing frequency of dosing and wastage of drug, optimized therapy and better patient compliances.

Effectual oral drug dispatch may depend upon the elements such as gastric emptying process, gastrointestinal transfer time of the dosage form, drug liberation from the dosage form and site of absorption of the drugs. As once the drug passes down the absorption site, the remaining quantity goes unabsorbed. Many of the oral dosage forms have much physiological reduction, such as a variable gastrointestinal transit because of changeable gastric unloading leading to non-uniform absorption profiles, insufficient drug release and small residence time of the dosage form in the stomach. This leads to incomplete absorption of drugs having an absorption window especially in the upper part of the small intestine. The gastric emptying of dosage forms in humans is pretentious by various elements. Because of which wide inter and intra subject variations are observed.

Since numerous drugs are well assimilated in the superior segment of the gastrointestinal tract, such high variability may lead to non-uniform absorption and makes the bioavailability uncertain. Hence a beneficial dispatch system would be one which possesses the ability to control and lengthen the gastric emptying time and can dispatch drugs in higher concentrations to the absorption site (i.e., superior segment of the small intestine)[1].

Gastro intestinal retention

Gastro retentive systems can persist in the gastric region for assorted hours and hence notably protract the gastric residence time of drugs.

Elongated gastric retention improves bioavailability, reduces drug waste and improves solubility for drugs that are less soluble in a high pH environment. It has a supplication also for local drug dispatch to the stomach and proximal small intestines. Gastro retention helps to provide better accessibility of new products with new therapeutic possibilities and substantial benefits for patients.

To successfully control the gastrointestinal transit time of a drug dispatch system across floating drug delivery system (FDDS) for supreme gastrointestinal absorption of drugs and site-specific delivery one needs to have a good fund [1].

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF FDDS

Advantages of FDDS

- Increase in bioavailability and curative efficiency of drugs and economic usage of dosage.
- Minimised factor of risk in resistance in antibiotics owing to stabilised therapeutic levels over prolonged periods removing fluctuations.
- Optimised release in case of short half-life drugs, causes flip flop pharmacokinetics and also ensures patient compliance with reduced dosage frequency.
- They are advantageous against drawbacks of the gastric retention time (GRT) as well as the gastric emptying time (GET). The system remains buoyant on gastric fluid because of lower bulk density than gastric fluids.
- These are efficient in repairing stomach and small intestine related problems. Its attributed to the fact that gastro retentive drug delivery sustains drug release and hence, avail local therapy in these organs.
- This method provides with a systematic and controlled drug delivery system which minimises chances of drug over exposure at the diseased site.
- Providing a narrow curative index, the gastro retentive dosage forms minimise variance in concentrations of drugs and effects.
- This system provides higher efficiency due to reduced counter activity by body.
- As the system provides with controlled rates of fluctuation, a wider array is provided for selectivity in receptor activation.

Disadvantages of FDDS

- Need for increased level of fluids in the stomach.
- Unsuitable for such drugs as:
- Problematic with solubility in gastric fluid
- Causing G.I irritation

Techniques of gastric retention

Floating systems have low bulk density, so that they can float on the gastric juice in the stomach. Diverse techniques were used to uplift gastric retention of an oral dosage form. The problem arises when the stomach is completely emptied of gastric fluid in such a situation; there is nothing to float on. Different techniques used for gastric retention are mentioned below;

1. Hydro dynamically balanced system (HBS) High-density system swelling system.
2. Expansion or Modified shape system.

Bio adhesive or Muco adhesive system Hydro dynamically balanced systems [2]

While the system is floating on the gastric contents the drug is leisurely released from the low density pellets or floating drug delivery systems are also called as hydro dynamically balanced systems (HBS). FDDS or HBS have a bulk density lower than gastric fluid, that is, bulk density of less than one [3]. HBS remains buoyant in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period of time and the drug is released slowly at a desired rate from the system [4]. After the release of the drug, the residual system is emptied from the stomach. The incorporated buoyant materials enable the device to float [5].

Modified shape systems:

Modified shape systems are non-disintegrating geometric shapes moulded from silastic elastomeric or exuded from polyethylene blends and extended the GIT depending on the size, shape and flexural modulus of the drug delivery device.

High-density system

Sedimentation has been recruited as a retention mechanism for pellets that are small enough to be maintained in the folds of the stomach body near the pyloric region, which is the part of the organ with the lowest situation in an upright posture. Dense pellets (approximately 3g/cm³) confined in fold also tend to withstand the peristaltic movements of the stomach wall. With pellets, the GI tract transit time can be increased from an average of 5.8 – 25 hours, depending more on density than on diameter of the pellets. Commonly used excipients are barium sulphate, zinc oxide, titanium dioxide and iron powder, etc. These materials increase density by up to 1.5-2.4g/cm³. This formulation of high-density pellet is based on assumption that heavy pellets might remain longer in the stomach, since they are position in the lower part of the pylorus. A number of other methods like use of passage-delaying agents and modified shape systems have also been used for gastro retention purpose.

Bio adhesive or mucous adhesive systems:

Bio adhesive system enabling the localized retention of the system in the stomach. The proposed mechanism of bio adhesive is the formation of hydrogen and electrostatic bonding at the mucus polymer boundary.

Swelling and expansion systems

The dosage forms are larger than the pyloric opening and so are retained in the stomach. There are some drawbacks associated with this approach; permanent retention of rigid large sized single-unit forms can cause bowel obstruction, intestinal adhesion and gastropathy. It can be referred as Plug-Type systems Polymers in the systems swell at a very faster rate and with higher degree to form a swollen matrix of which size is greater than that of the pylorus. The rate and extent of swelling are important parameters. The rate of swelling and rate erosion are also important.

Single-unit dosage forms**Low density approach of single unit dosage forms**

In low density approach the spherical shells evidently possess low density than that of gastric fluid can be used as a bearer for drug for its controlled release. A buoyant dosage form can also be obtained by using a fluid-filled system that floats in the stomach. In covered shells popcorn, pop rice and polystyrol have been utilized as drug carriers. Sugar polymeric substances such as meth acrylic polymer and cellulose acetate phthalate have been used to undercoat these shells. These are furthermore coated with a drug polymer mixture. The polymer of choice can be either ethyl cellulose or hydroxypropylcellulose depending upon the type of release inclined. Finally, the product floats on the gastric fluid while releasing the drug slowly over a prolonged duration.

Hydro dynamically balanced systems (HBS)

HBS system containing a homogenous mixture of drug and a hydrocolloid in a capsule which upon contact with gastric fluid acquired and maintained a bulk density less than 1, thereby being buoyant on the gastric contents of stomach until all the drug was released. The HBS is a novel dosage form which when in contact with gastric fluid and after dissolution of outer exposed surface of the dosage form, forms a hydrated gel layer and maintained bulk density less than 1g/cm³. Thus this system remains buoyant in the gastric fluid inside the stomach for 6hrs. The increase in retention time of HBS may also be due to effects the adhesion to the gastric mucosa, rather than the effect of floating. Conventional dosage form disintegrate within 60minutes and are emptied totally from the stomach shortly afterwards. This dosage form releases the drug through the hydrated layer by diffusion principle. This system is valuable for drugs which are soluble at lower pH and have an absorption window in the upper GIT.

By varying the composition of the excipient between 25% to 75%w/w of one or more gel forming hydrocolloids such as hydroxyl ethyl cellulose, hydroxyl propyl cellulose, hydroxyl propyl methylcellulose and sodium carboxy methylcellulose, the granules are prepared and compressed into tablets or encapsulated into capsules, which results in the desired release rate of drug.

This hydrated gel controls the rate of solvent penetration into the device and the rate of drug release from the device. Floating drug delivery device with self- activated mechanism for retaining the device in the stomach, which releases the drug under controlled osmotic pressure. The device was found to consist of two chambers, one for the drug reservoir and the other osmogen. In the stomach the gastric fluid dissolves the osmogen, which creates pressure on the drug reservoir compartment; this pressure tends to reduce the total volume of the drug reservoir compartment thereby leading to the continuous release of the drug material from the device. Next approach is the HBS capsule for the sustained release of the drug in the stomach by incorporation of liquid such as ether in an inflatable chamber.

These are designed to prolong the stay of the dosage form in the gastrointestinal tract as an aid in enhancing the absorption. Such systems are best suited for drugs having better solubility in acidic environment and also for the drugs having specific site of absorption in the upper part of small intestine. To remain in the stomach for an extended span of time the dosage form must have a bulk density of less than 1. It should stay in the stomach, conserve its structural integrity and liberate drug continuously from the dosage form. However, there may be scarce exceptions, where the presence or absence of food, the stomach has no effect on the absorption of a drug from HBS type dosage forms. The success of HBS capsule as a better system is best exemplified with chlorodiazepoxide hydrochloride comparable blood level time profile as of three 10-mg commercial capsules. The drug is an example of a solubility problem where in it displays a 4000-fold dissimilar in solubility going from pH 3 to 6 (the solubility of chlorodiazepoxide hydrochloride is 150mg/ml and is ~0.1mg/ml at neutral pH).

Multiple-unit dosage form

Single unit formulations are associated with problems such as sticking together or being obstructed in gastrointestinal tract, which may have a potential danger of producing irritation. Multiple unit systems avoid the 'all-or-none' gastric emptying nature of single unit systems. It reduces the inter subject variability in absorption and the probability for dose dumping is lower. In carbon dioxide-generating multiple-unit oral formulations several devices with features that extend, unfold, or are inflated by carbon dioxide generated in the devices after administration have been described in the recent patent literature [5].

Classification of floating drug delivery systems

Based on the mechanism of buoyancy two distinctly dissimilar technologies, have been utilized in the development of FDDS:

1. Effervescent system

- 1) Volatile liquid containing systems
- 2) Gas generating systems

2. Non-effervescent system

- 1) Colloidal gel barrier systems
- 2) Micro porous compartment system
- 3) Alginate beads
- 4) Hollow microspheres / Microballons

Effervescent System

Gas-generating Systems:

These light (floating) delivery systems use bubbling reactions between carbonate/bicarbonate salts and citric/tartaric acid to liberate CO₂ which gets entrapped in the jellified hydrocolloid layer of the systems thus decreasing its specific gravity and making it to float over chyme. The optimal stoichiometric ratio of citric acid and sodium bicarbonate for gas generation is reported to be 0.76:1. A prepared a multiple unit floating pill, which consisted of a core seed surrounded by two different layers. The primary layer contained sodium bicarbonate and tartaric acid, which generated carbon dioxide in aqueous media. The outer layer collected of a swellable membrane that trapped the gas resulting in flotation of the system. The system started floating within 10 minutes of immersion into the test media and remained floated over a period of 5 hours. A prepared coated ion interchange resin beads as gastro retentive delivery system. The resin had been charged with bicarbonate before it was coated with a semi permeable membrane of eudragit. In the presence of hydrochloric acid bicarbonate was liberated, which formed carbon dioxide. The later was trapped inside the membrane resulting in flotation of the resin particle. It has been developed a prolonged gastro retentive delivery system by combining both floating and bio adhesive techniques. They used ion exchange resins loaded with bicarbonate and acetohydroxamic acid; the particles were then coated with cellulose acetate butyrate by emulsion solvent evaporation method. The system exhibited floating ability due to the carbon dioxide generation when micro granules were revealed to gastric fluid. The mucoadhesiveness of the micro particles was examined by employing fluorescent probe. It was advanced as a swellable unsymmetrical triple layer tablet with buoyant ability to extend the gastric residence time of triple drug regimen (tetracycline, metronidazole, and clarithromycin) in helicobacter pylori associated peptic ulcer.

Using HPMC and poly ethylene oxide (PEO) as the rate managing polymeric membrane excipient. The buoyant was attained by incorporating gas-generating layer consisting of sodium bicarbonate or calcium carbonate along with polymers. The in-vivo results revealed that the assisted delivery of tetracycline and metronidazole over 6-8 hours could be arrived while the tablet persists afloat.

Volatile liquid containing systems:

The GRT of a drug delivery system can be assisted by integrating an inflatable chamber, which contains a liquid e.g. ether, cyclopentane, that gasifies at body temperature to cause the inflation of the chamber in the stomach. The device may also consist of a bio erodible plug made up of PVA, Polyethylene, etc. that gradually dissolves causing the inflatable chamber to release gas and collapse after a predetermined time to permit the spontaneous ejection of the inflatable systems from the stomach.

Non Effervescent System:

This type of system followed by swallowing, swells uncontrolled via... Imbibitions of gastric fluid to an extent that it prevents their exit from the stomach. These systems may be referred to as the 'plug-type systems' since they have a propensity to remain lodged near the pyloric sphincter. One of the formulation methods of such dosage forms necessitates the mixing of drug with a gel, which swells in contact with gastric fluid after oral administration and maintains a relative integrity of shape and a bulk density of less than one within the outer gelatinous barrier. The air trapped by the swollen polymer confers lightness to this dosage forms. The most frequently used ingredients in non bubbling buoyant drug delivery system are gel devising or highly swellable cellulose type hydrocolloids, polysaccharides and matrix devising polymers such as polyacrylate, polymethacrylate and polycarbonate. After oral administration these dosage form swells in contact with gastric fluid and achieves a bulk density. The air entangled within the swollen matrix imparts buoyancy to the dosage form.

Colloidal gel barrier systems:

- Such systems contains drug with gel devising hydrocolloids meant to endure buoyant on stomach contents.
- These systems incorporate a high level of one or more gel devising highly swellable cellulose type hydrocolloids. E.g. HEC, HPMC, NaCMC.
- On coming in touch with gastric fluid forms a viscous core.
- Incorporates H₂O and ensnares air.
- Density of system falls below 1gm/cm³. Then it begins floating [6].

Formulating agents of FDDS

Following types of the constituents can be incorporated in to HBS dosage form:

- Active Ingredients.
- Hydrocolloids.
- Inert fatty materials.
- Release rate accelerants.
- Release rate retardants.
- Buoyancy increasing agents.
- Miscellaneous.

Active Ingredients:

The active ingredients that to be formulated into FDDS, must possess the absorption window in the gastric region. Some of the examples of the drugs that are to be formulated into FDDS are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Ideal candidates for making FDDS with respective dosage forms [7-15].

S.No	Dosage Forms	Drugs
1	Coating microspheres	Aspirin, Griseofulvin, p-nitro aniline, Ibuprofen, Terfinadine and Tranilast.
2	Floating granules	Diclofenac sodium, Indomethacin and Prednisolone.
3	Films	Cinnarizine, Chlordiazepoxide, Hydrogen chloride, Diazepam, Furosemide, Misoprostol, L-Dopa, Benserazide, Ursodeoxycholic acid
4	Floating Capsules	And Pepstatin. Acetaminophen, Acetylsalicylic acid, Ampicillin, Amoxicillin trihydrate, Atenolol, Diltiazem, Fluorouracil, Isosorbide mononitrate, Para- aminobenzoic acid,
5	Coating tablets and Pills	Piretamide, Theophylline and Verapamil hydrochloride.

Hydrocolloids

Suitable hydrocolloids are synthetics, anionic or non ionic like hydrophilic gums, changed cellulose derivatives. E.g. Acacia, pectin, agar, alginates, gelatin, casein, bentonite, veegum, methylcellulose, hydroxypropylcellulose and hydroxyethylcellulose and carboxymethylcellulose sodium can be used. The hydrocolloids must hydrate in acidic medium i.e. gastric fluid is having pH 1.2.

Inert fatty materials

Edible, pharmaceutical inert fatty substance, having a specific gravity less than one can be adjoined to the formulation to decrease the hydrophilic property of formulation and hence increases the buoyancy. E.g. Purified grades of beeswax, fatty acids, long chain alcohols, glycerides, and mineral oils can be used.

Release rate accelerants

The release rate of the medicament from the formulation can be modified by including excipient like lactose and/or mannitol. These may be present from about 5-60% by weight.

Release rate retardants

Insoluble substances such as calcium phosphate, talc, magnesium stearate decreased the solubility and hence retard the release of medicaments.

Buoyancy increasing agents

Materials like ethyl cellulose, which has bulk density less than one, can be used for intensifying the buoyancy of the formulation. It may be adapted up to 80 % by weight.

Miscellaneous

Pharmaceutically acceptable adjuvant like preservatives, stabilizers, and lubricants can be incorporates in the dosage forms as per the requirements. They do not adversely affect the hydrodynamic balance of the systems [16].

Evaluation of floating dosage forms:

Different parameters that require to be evaluated comprises floating duration, particle size analysis, flow properties, surface morphology, differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), incorporation efficiency, and micromeritic properties such as tapped density, true density etc. are also evaluated. Techniques such as γ scintigraphy, radiology, gastroscopy, ultrasonography, and MRI are also used for the evaluation. The test for floating behaviour and drug release are generally executed in simulated gastric fluids 37°C. It is characterized that buoyancy capability of floating forms and sinking of non floating dosage forms using as apparatus to quantitatively measure the total floating force acting vertically on the immersed object. The apparatus operates by measuring continuously the force equivalent to F (as a function of time), which is required to maintain the submerged object. The object floats better if F is on the higher positive side.

$F = f(\text{buoyancy}) - f(\text{gravity})$
 $F = (D_b - D_s) gV$
 F – Total vertical force
 D_s – Object density
 D_b – fluid density
 V- Volume of fluid
 g- Acceleration due to gravity.

Swelling studies

Swelling studies were carried out using USP dissolution apparatus-II (rotating paddle), in 900 ml of 0.1N HCl which is maintained at 37±0.5°C, rotated at 50 rpm. Weight of individual tablet was taken prior to the swelling study (W₁). The tablet was kept in a basket. The tablet was removed every one hour interval up to 12 hour and excess water removed carefully using filter paper. The swollen tablets were re-weighed (W₂); Percent hydration (swelling index) was calculated by using following formula,

$$\% \text{ Swelling Index} = \{(W_2 - (W_1 / (W_1)) \times 100$$

Where

W₁ – initial weight of tablet

W₂ – weight of swollen tablet [17].

In-vitro drug release/dissolution studies:

In-vitro drug release study of was carried in 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2), for a period of 8 -24h. Temperature 37° c ± 0.5° C. *In-vitro* release studies were carried out by using United States Pharmacopoeia (USP) 23 Dissolution Testing Apparatus II (Paddle method). The dissolution test was performed using 900 ml of 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2) at 37±0.5°C. 50 rpm was maintained, 5 ml of sample was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals for 24 hours and the same volume of the fresh medium was replaced [18].

A simple method for determining the floating behaviour can be used. A definite no. of particles were placed into 0.1 N HCl, pH 1.2, containing 0.02% w/v tween 20(37°C) to exclude floating due to non wetted surfaces, followed by horizontal shaking. At predetermined time intervals, the flasks were allowed to stand for 5 minutes, without agitation and the no of settled particles was counted. Surface morphology was observed by SEM and with the help of particle size analyzer; particle size distribution can be evaluated [6].

Scintigraphy [19]

A technique in which a scintillation counter or similar detector is used with a radioactive tracer to obtain an image of a bodily organ or a record of its functioning.

Radiography [20]

Radiography is an using X-rays to view the internal structure of an object. To create the image, a beam of X-rays, a form of electromagnetic radiation, are produced by an X-ray generator and are projected toward the object. A certain amount of X-ray is absorbed by the object, dependent on its density and composition.

Gastroscopy [21]

It is an examination of the upper digestive tract (the oesophagus, stomach and duodenum) using an endoscope which is a long, thin, flexible tube containing a camera and a light to view the lining of these organs.

Ultra sonography [22]

A technique using echoes of ultrasound pulses to delineate objects or areas of different density in the body.

CONCLUSION

In current scenario various scientific and technological advancements have been made in the research and development of Gastro Retentive Drug Delivery Systems (GRDDS). Many efforts have been made to increase the retention time of the drug-delivery systems for more than 12 hours with floating type of formulations in these days. FDDS has emerged as an efficient means of enhancing the bioavailability and controlled delivery of many drugs. The increasing sophistication of delivery technology will ensure the development of increasing number of gastro retentive drug delivery systems such as floating drug delivery system to optimize the delivery of molecules that exhibit narrow absorption window, low bioavailability and extensive first pass metabolism. Now a day's gastro intestinal transit time was controlled with sophisticated techniques such as smart pill endoscopy as the main focus and resulting in new therapeutic possibilities with substantial benefits for patient.

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